

The effect of injection therapies on surgery rates in persons with radicular pain from a herniated lumbar disc – a systematic literature review

APPENDIX 1 - Search strategies for five publication databases

Cochrane Library

ID	Search term	# hits 05.09.25
#1	(radiating NEAR/3 pain):ti,ab,kw	601
#2	MeSH descriptor: [Radiculopathy] this term only	787
#3	MeSH descriptor: [Sciatica] this term only	423
#4	radicul* OR ischialgi* or sciatic*:ti,ab,kw	6,419
#5	(slipped OR prolaps* OR displace* or hernia*) NEAR/3 (disc or discs or disk or disks):ti,ab,kw	4,138
#6	MeSH descriptor: [Intervertebral Disc Displacement] this term only	1,410
#7	disc herniation:ti,ab,kw	2,332
#8	MeSH descriptor: [Spinal Nerve Roots] this term only	257
#9	MeSH descriptor: [Injections, Spinal] explode all trees	1,818
#10	MeSH descriptor: [Nerve Block] this term only	6,075
#11	(epidural or foraminal or transforaminal or extraforaminal or perineural or periradicular) NEAR/3 (injection* or block*):ti,ab,kw	4,210
#12	nerve NEAR/3 (injection* or block*):ti,ab,kw	17,767
#13	Transforaminal epidural steroid injection*:ti,ab,kw	284
#14	TFESI:ti,ab,kw	88
#15	Selective nerve root block*:ti,ab,kw	95
#16	SNRB:ti,ab,kw	23
#17	{or #1-#8}	9,787
#18	{or #9-#16}	22,367
#19	#17 and #18	2,132

EMBASE SEARCH STRATEGY		
		# hits 05.01.26
1	exp radiculopathy/	55,606
2	sciatica/	4,575
3	intervertebral disk hernia/ or lumbar disk hernia/	35,613
4	(radicul* or ischialgi* or sciatic* or radiating pain or ((slipped or prolaps* or displace* or hernia*) adj3 (disc or discs or disk or disks))).ti,ab,kf	100,469
5	spinal root/	6,508
6	or/ 1-5	155,877
7	exp intraspinal drug administration/	37,946
8	exp epidural drug administration/	10,293
9	exp nerve block/	69,253
10	((epidural or foraminal or transforaminal or extraforaminal or perineural or periradicular) adj3 (injection* or block*)).ti,ab,kf	13,310
11	TFESI.ti,ab,kf	394
12	SNRB.ti,ab,kf	129
13	or/ 7-12	113,740
14	6 and 13	10,253
15	((exp animal/ or nonhuman/) NOT exp human/)	8,797,015
16	14 not 15	9,121
17	limit 16 to (books or chapter or "clinical trial (clinicaltrials.gov)" or conference abstract or conference paper or "conference review")	3,115
18	16 not 17	6,006

MEDLINE SEARCH STRATEGY

		# hits 05.01.26
1	Radiculopathy/	6,313
2	Sciatica/	5,282
3	Intervertebral disc displacement/	21,410
4	Spinal nerve roots/	10,733
5	((radicul* or ischialgi* or sciatic* or radiating pain) or ((slipped or prolaps* or displace* or hernia*) ADJ3 (disc or discs or disk or disks))). ti,ab,kf	73,186
6	OR/ 1-5	91,219
7	exp Injections, Spinal/	17,994
8	Nerve block/	23,964
9	(epidural or foraminal or transforaminal or extraforaminal or perineural or periradicular) ADJ3 (injection* or block*). ti,ab,kf	8,281
10	TFESI. ti,ab,kf	251
11	Selective nerve root block*. ti,ab,kf	218
12	SNRB. ti,ab,kf	93
13	OR/ 7-12	46,732
14	6 AND 13	4,868
15	Exp Animals/ not humans.sh.	5,410,731
16	14 NOT 15	4,042

SCOPUS SEARCH STRATEGY

hits 30.09.25

SEARCH 1

TITLE-ABS-KEY(((radiating w/3 pain) OR (radicul* OR ischialgi* OR sciatic*) OR ((slipped OR prolaps* OR displace* OR hernia*) w/3 (disc OR discs OR disk OR disks)) OR (lumbosacral OR "nerve root")) AND (((nerve OR epidural OR foraminal OR transforaminal OR extraforaminal OR perineural OR periradicular) w/3 (injection* OR block*)) OR (TFESI OR SNRB)))

hits: 9,956

SEARCH 2

TITLE-ABS-KEY ({animal experiment} OR {animal model} OR {experimental animal} OR animal OR animals OR nonhuman OR {animal tissue} OR mouse OR rat)

hits: 11,758,831

SEARCH 3

1 AND 2

hits: 2,146

SEARCH 4

1 AND NOT 3

hits: 7,810

WEB OF SCIENCE SEARCH STRATEGY

	Code	# hits 30.09.25
1	TS=(radiat* near/3 pain)	3,820
2	TS=(radicul* OR ischialgi* OR sciatic*)	60,696
3	TS=((slipped OR prolapse* OR displace* OR hernia*) near/3 (disc OR disk OR discs OR disks))	21,552
4	TS=("nerve root*")	13,804
5	TS=(TFESI OR SNRB)	322
6 POPULATION	TS=((radiat* near/3 pain) OR (radicul* OR ischialgi* OR sciatic*) OR ((slipped OR prolapse* OR displace* OR hernia*) near/3 (disc OR disk OR discs OR disks)) OR ("nerve root*"))	89,097
7 INTERVENTION	TS=(((epidural OR foraminal OR transforaminal OR extraforaminal OR perineural OR periradicular OR nerve) near/3 (injection* OR block*)) OR (TFESI OR SNRB))	36,269
8 FULL SEARCH	(TS=(((radiat* near/3 pain) OR (radicul* OR ischialgi* OR sciatic*) OR ((slipped OR prolapse* OR displace* OR hernia*) near/3 (disc OR disk OR discs OR disks)) OR ("nerve root*")))) AND TS=(((epidural OR foraminal OR transforaminal OR extraforaminal OR perineural OR periradicular OR nerve) near/3 (injection* OR block*)) OR (TFESI OR SNRB))	6,432